

JOB CHARACTERISTICS AS PREDICTORS OF WORK OUTCOMES OF INTERN STUDENTS

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Abstract

Today, colleges and universities must deal with rapid changes in employability. An internship is crucial for students to learn to adapt to the workplace. This research contributes to the literature by filling the research gap on management students' virtual internships. This study aimed to determine if job characteristics are antecedent to the work outcomes of students during their virtual internship. The research design is correlational, and a random sampling technique was used to get a sample size of 150 business management intern students from one state university in the Philippines. Regression analysis was employed to analyze the data. The findings revealed that task variety, the significance of tasks, and feedback predict work outcomes. Moreover, the results showed that job characteristics and work outcomes have a positive relationship. It leads to the recommendation that presenting the importance of tasks, doing multi-tasks, and providing feedback on performance are crucial to ensure better work outcomes for intern students. The limitation of this study is that the participants were virtual intern students who were assigned to do tasks at home without supervision, which somehow affected their opinions when answering the survey questionnaire.

Keywords: Job characteristics, work outcomes, intern students, virtual internship, predictors

INTRODUCTION

Programs that connect classroom learning with the reality of the workplace give students a hands-on learning opportunity and prepare them to compete in the modern competitive environment. The employment experience of students who have completed a work placement is consistently related to higher employment rates (Smith et al., 2018). The education and work experience of students and graduates is underpinned by an internship program (Vinay, 2022). Internship programs form part of the curriculum at colleges and universities. It became a requisite in higher education to assist students with real-life work experience, provide job opportunities, and prepare them for future employment.

Since the implementation of the lockdown due to the coronavirus, traditional on-site internships are no longer possible for many students. Internship programs have changed, with 40% delaying the start date, 40% shifting to the internet through a virtual internship, and 20% reducing the number of intern students (Hess, 2020). As a result, virtual internships become more popular as a great substitute. A virtual internship runs a comprehensive employability program that enhances a student's career readiness skills, their employability possibilities, and equips them for the future of work, according to a Times Higher Education article (Student, 2022). For learners who are involved in many works, volunteer, and have other commitments, a virtual internship is ideal since it can give them more scheduling flexibility. Most virtual

internships allow interns time to finish a particular job before giving them additional duties. Virtual interns execute responsibilities from home in a variety of tasks that need remote work, corresponding with managers and team members thru email, video chat, and other technologies (Carlton, 2022). It enables the intern to accomplish work in their own time. According to Ahmed et al. (2014), as cited in Fitriani, et al. (2021), most employees report feeling motivated when working from home, which brings positive results in their job competence and skills. As per Nicholson & Baruch's (1997) research, self-motivation is perceived as most needed by employees who work independently at home (as cited in Fitriani, et al. 2021).

Research on how internship programs assist business students in their workplace, particularly in developing countries, is limited (Anjum, 2020). Hence, this paper adds to the existing knowledge. This study examined job characteristics as predictors of work outcomes of intern students taking Bachelor of Science in Business Management majors in Human Resources, Marketing, and Finance at one state university in the Philippines during their virtual internship. This paper also aimed to assess the level of job characteristics as perceived by intern students and their degree of agreement on the work outcomes. The results of this study can help human resource managers determine which of the core characteristics of a job must be designed toward intern students' motivation, satisfaction, and productivity. In addition, the findings could help the institution and partner firms determine a proactive solution to the reinforcement of job designs that suits the needs of virtual internships.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Nevertheless, students' experience in a partnership firm is always valued. Career centers work harder to promote internship participation and put students in jobs that suit them and their academic objectives, thus linking internship satisfaction and academic achievement (Gibson, 2017). Caraig (2018) revealed that in one university in the Philippines the intern students did very satisfactorily throughout their internship, and the student-trainees were delighted with the industrial immersion program. However, according to Wu & Wu (2006), as quoted in Salatan (2016) after their apprenticeship, many students lack confidence in their future in the industry. The lack of adequate time for training and supervision, a lack of positive working relationships, and unclear instructions are some of the issues that interns think about in the workplace.

Job Characteristics

Essentially, considering job characteristics in practice escalates the meaningfulness of the job. To encourage people to work, organizations need to offer jobs that are in demand and satisfy their workers. One strategy used to satisfy workers is to design a work that integrates job characteristics (Prameswari, 2019). Job characteristics stimulate the tasks of employees to become more appealing, varied, and highly challenging (Anthia, 2020).

The researchers adopt the Job Characteristics model developed in 1974 by Hackman and Oldham in this study. Today, this model became part of the work design or job design, where the focus is on defining a role to fulfill the requirements of both the company and the individual. Jobs are restructured to involve employees in every step of making a product to improve

productivity. The Job Characteristics theory shows that job characteristics have an impact on performance (outcomes) through important psychological states that drive motivation. The theory asserts that how people view occupations in terms of the five essential job requirements: autonomy, task importance, task identity, skill variety, and feedback affect three specific psychological responses to the job. Making meaningful experiences at work, emphasizing the importance of being responsible at work, and knowing the job will lead to more satisfied, motivated, and productive employees (Hussein, 2020).

A variety of skills is a core characteristic of a job and is concerned with the abilities needed to execute a job. A variety of skills is needed to perform the many tasks assigned to the workers. They can feel the meaningfulness of what they do if their jobs require several skills. Individual morale may increase if the organization promotes team members' use of diverse skills because it will lessen monotony and boost motivation and job satisfaction. It was found that competent management of an employee's well-being not only increased productivity but also helped develop the character of the person, making them more effective at their work and multitasking (Andrew et al., 2016). The different skills of employees help them complete the tasks appropriately while discerning the meaning of the job. Northern IOWA Therapy-Occupational report in 2020 that in US workplaces, people who manage a variety of duties at work are more likely to be innovative since doing so stimulates their brains in novel ways. Many workers use a variety of abilities rather than having jobs that are boring in nature or function. Yet, adding a wide variety of skills that the employee finds unpleasant, is ill-suited to handle, or simply adding minimal obligations and skills without increasing the intrinsic value of the job could have the reverse impact and raise dissatisfaction (Benjamin, n.d.). Another core of the job is task identity, when workers are involved in the completion of recognizable work it could result in a more meaningful feeling for them. A method of raising employee motivation levels is through task identity. Task identity is a core characteristic of the job that occurs when workers fulfill work from start to finish with a visible result. It refers to how much a job requires an engagement to carry out every task necessary to complete it from the beginning to the end of the production process. Moreso, employees that enjoy autonomy at work have control over the manner and timing of their job (Wooll, 2021). Autonomy is considered essential to the job. When workers are given freedom, independence, and discretion in planning their work and determining the procedures they use to carry it out, they will be motivated. Intrinsically motivated people carry out an activity that they find fascinating, that gives novelty, and optimal challenge. Evans et al. (2020) revealed from a study conducted at one Australian university that one of the factors of job satisfaction for midwifery students is the ability to make autonomous midwifery decisions. Nevertheless, imparting the importance of each assignment to their employees is necessary. Employees become more engaged and can feel greater trust and respect if they know that the task assigned to them is crucial for the organization. To develop them, managers, staff, and supervisors must assist in finding fulfillment in their work. Recent studies have revealed that employees who find meaning in their work tend to perform better and are more invested in their job (Blando, 2019). Feedback is necessary, by providing information about the effectiveness of the performance employees become more motivated. Communicating with employees working from home is challenging, but employers

must provide feedback. Feedback is assessing the work to determine if the employee is satisfied and able to accomplish the desired objective. It allows a better understanding of what is needed to improve. As per Wong and Wee (2020), feedback evaluates the tasks that enable the person doing the job to have immediate access to information about how well their performance is working. Feedback can therefore enhance their performance depending on the comments or input obtained.

As per Hackman & Oldham (1974), the characteristics of a job include elements that impact comprehension of work, a sense of accountability for work outcomes, concern for changes resulting from work, and acceptable politeness norms for employees, all of which may further boost work engagement (as cited in Prameswari, 2019). Knowing the task & role characteristics in an organization plays a vital role in how an employee engages or performs in the workplace. When an employee is highly interested and motivated on their task/roles, their engagement towards the work will surely be noticeable in a positive way. Employees' point of view in task characteristics is valuable to revitalize employee engagement at work. A good perception of task characteristics leads to employees' engagement towards their work. Which means that the employer should consider designing jobs that caters the task characteristics to advocate employee engagement even further, for example, assigning more independent and challenging tasks (George et al., 2020).

Work Outcome

Nowadays, businesses are very concerned on employee engagement due to the fact that it has a significant impact on organizational performance. The success of the organization in achieving its objectives relies on overall performance of employees and it depends on their motivational levels. Actions and outputs should be directed at achieving results (Pant, 2018).

Jobs can impact an employee's performance, dedication, commitment, and motivation. When objectives are met, work effectiveness takes place. The productivity, motivation, and task performance are associated with job satisfaction. Employee morale and motivation are integrally tied to work outcomes. The outcomes are the most valuable and significant aspects of work. Effective performance starts with an employee's understanding of their roles and how they will impact company goals. When work effectiveness is achieved and practiced, employees can optimize efficiency, which helps them see the big picture while prioritizing productivity in achieving assigned work outcomes (Martins, 2021). Highly satisfied employees are technically regular and punctual with their deadlines, engaged, and pleased with their lives, influencing their behavior or attitudes in producing work outcomes Lease (1998), quoted in Inayat & Khan (2021).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A correlational research design was used by the researchers. The correlational analysis is frequently used by researchers to examine connections between various study variables. Research designs that examine the connections between two or more variables are known as

correlational studies. Studies that use correlation are non-experimental, which means that no variables are changed or under the experimenter's control (Cherry, 2022). The researchers endeavor to measure the relationship between the independent variable job characteristics core dimensions with the dependent variable work outcome (Figure 1).

Hypotheses

Ho 1 to Ho 4 state that predictor variables core dimensions of job characteristics; job autonomy, task variety, task significance, and feedback have no significant relationship with work outcomes. The regression model had work outcomes as the dependent variable and job characteristics as independent variables (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Research Framework

Data Gathering Procedure

A proposed letter was given to the Office of the Registrar of a state university in the Philippines to determine the number of intern students. The sample size of 150 was generated using the Raosoft sampling calculator from the total population of 245 intern students. The 150 students of Bachelor of Science in Business Management majors in Human Resources, Marketing, and Finance in one state university in the Philippines under a virtual internship program were the participants of this study. A random sampling technique was utilized in this study. The participants were surveyed using an online survey. After that, the information was analyzed using MS Excel Data Analysis Tool.

Research Instrument

The researchers used a self-made questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of two parts. Part 1 of the questionnaire for the level of intensity of job characteristics was adopted from the study of Zacher et al. (2017). The second part about work outcomes was a self-made questionnaire by the researchers. The instrument developed was validated by experts with a high-reliability result of .895 on Cronbach's alpha.

The level of job characteristics is composed of 12 adopted questions and was structured using the typical five-level Likert rating from (1) very low to (5) very high. The 15 questions for work outcomes were structured using the Likert rating of (1) = Strongly Disagree to (5) = Strongly Agree (Table 1).

Table 1: Likert Scale Scaling Range and Verbal Interpretation

Rate	Rating Scale	Degree of Agreement	Level of intensity
4.21 – 5.00	5	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	4	Agree	High
2.21 – 3.40	3	Moderately Agree/Disagree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.20	2	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	1	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Statistical Treatment

The researchers utilized regression analysis, standard deviation, and mean. The data were analyzed using the MS Excel Data Analysis Tool Pack. The simple mathematical average of two or more numbers is the mean. The standard deviation indicates how widely distributed a dataset is concerning its mean. It is a statistic that computes the square root of the variance. To analyze the relationships between the variables multiple regression was employed. R2 in multiple regressions represents the percentage of the dependent variable's variation (Makera, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Presented in Table 2 are response on the perceived level of job characteristics by the participants.

Table 2: Perception of intern students on the job characteristics level of intensity

Job Characteristics Core Dimensions	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Job Autonomy			
1. The job gives me a chance to use my personal initiative or judgment in carrying out the work	4.03	1.07	High
2. The job allows me to make decisions on my own	3.21	1.37	Moderate
3. The job provides me with autonomy in making decisions	3.82	1.19	High
Task Variety			
4. The job involves performing a variety of tasks.	4.51	0.65	Very High
5. The job involves doing a number of different things.	4.48	0.70	Very High
6. The job requires the performance of a wide range of tasks.	4.45	0.66	Very High
Task Significance			

7. The results of work significantly affect the lives of other people.	3.55	1.33	High
8. The work performed on the job has an impact on people outside the organization.	4.28	0.84	Very High
9. The job has an impact on people outside the organization.	4.25	0.82	Very High
Feedback from the Job			
10. The work activities provide direct and clear information about the effectiveness of job performance.	4.45	0.74	Very High
11. The job itself provides feedback	4.44	0.72	Very High
12. The job itself provides information about the performance.	4.31	0.79	Very High

Legend: 1.00-1.80=Very Low; 1.81-2.60=Low; 2.61-3.40= Moderate; 3.41- 4.20=High; 4.21-5.00=Very High

In terms of job autonomy, the result reveals that the highest weighted mean of 4.03 is on the statement number one on which the participants perceived to be “High”. It implies that the student interns can be independent and can work without constantly needing to be told what to do. It was found from the study by Schall (2019) that a higher perception of independence was related to higher satisfaction with one’s job. From among the results presented, the lowest generated mean for job characteristics is the statement number 2 from job autonomy, which got the lowest of 3.21 which is verbally interpreted as “Moderate”. It implies the objectivity of the job provided by the organizations to student interns. Students can anticipate that the supervisor will provide them with information and clear instructions to complete their internship job Youngblood (2020). Not allowing the student interns to make their own decision in doing the job is expected because students are only trainees during the internship program. Based on the table presented, the participant's responses to task variety. Statement number 4 got the highest mean of 4.51, which the participants perceived to be “Very High,” followed by statement number 5. It implies that student interns perform multiple tasks at work. The creativity of the students who multitask produced significantly more ideas for the bricks than the students who did not. Their analytical performance was unaffected by. However, Khanna (2021) stated that students view multitasking as an essential component of their daily lives. Yet, this is only feasible if one or more jobs are learned to the level where no cognitive thought is required to accomplish them. In terms of task significance, the statement number 8 generated the highest weighted mean of 4.28, with a “Very High” level of intensity based on the perception of intern students. It indicates that the participants are well aware of the fact that the value of the work done in the workplace extends outside of the organization and nonetheless profoundly influences other people's lives. Task significance is a measure of how much a job contributes to the organization's or the world's overall efforts. It thus measures how much a worker believes that their work significantly affects other people's lives (Cloudfare, n.d)

For job feedback, the statement number 10 obtained the highest mean of 4.45 with a verbal interpretation of strongly agree. The result implies that students need to be well guided with instruction and clear information to complete the assignment with ease. According to Mina, Garcia & Reyes (2020), it is crucial that the campus is aware of the feedback of the trainers/supervisors to the student performance during their training because the quality of internship learning is largely dependent on the of comments and monitoring provided by both the firm and the university. This occurs in connection with the university's ongoing efforts to fulfill its commitment to its stakeholders. Moreover, this can serve as a starting point for further developing the existing program.

Table 3 presents the result on degree of agreement for work outcomes. The statement " I am motivated to complete several tasks and see the result, generated the highest mean of 4.65 which is verbally interpreted as "Strongly Agree", followed by the statement "The feeling or sense of accomplishment in completing my work is strengthen" with a mean of 4.56. It indicates that intern students were motivated to complete the assignment that was new to them, and they were eager to see the outcome of their work. This is supported by Mustamiah and Widanti (2020) who affirmed that learning motivation could influence student engagement.

While the statement "I am satisfied with the recognition and appreciation by the organization for my job well done" got the lowest mean of 2.75, verbally interpreted as "Neutral". The result signifies that the students are not given recognition on the job. The study of Bureau et al. (2021) divulged that if students are properly mentored, it provides the trainees with a satisfying internship experience, which leads to greater performance results internship.

Table 3: Intern students' degree of agreement on the work outcomes

Work Outcome	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Establishing skill variety in the job affects my eagerness in discovering new talents and abilities.	4.52	0.68	Strongly Agree
I am motivated to complete several tasks and see the result	4.65	0.64	Strongly Agree
My tasks stimulate my drive to contribute at work more than what is expected.	4.52	0.76	Strongly Agree
My interest to do several different tasks and activities is supported by the firm	4.31	0.79	Strongly Agree
The significance of task encourages me to continually improve my performance for the best results.	3.87	1.06	Agree
Performing the job brings me pleasure	4.5	0.65	Strongly Agree
The task allows me to reach the highest potential within the organization.	4.43	0.82	Strongly Agree
I am satisfied with the recognition and appreciation by the organization for my job well done	2.75	1.39	Neutral
The feeling or sense of accomplishment in completing my work is strengthen	4.56	0.76	Strongly Agree
Taking challenging tasks at work is fulfilled	4.41	0.82	Strongly Agree

The job helps me in the effective utilization of various skills and abilities at work.	4.38	0.82	Strongly Agree
The task gives rise to recognition of outcomes of my activities or tasks.	4.49	0.73	Strongly Agree
The tasks intensify my initiatives at work.	4.51	0.76	Strongly Agree
Achieving expected results is met in my tasks	4.51	0.69	Strongly Agree
My sense of contribution to the job is supported by the organization	4.54	0.64	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1 – Strongly disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Neutral, 4 – Agree, 5 – Strongly agree.

Table 4: Relationship between job characteristics and work outcome

Job Characteristics		Correlation coefficient	P-value	Remarks	Decision
Job Autonomy	Work Outcome	0.38	0.133	Not significant	Accept the null hypothesis
Task Variety		0.60	.001	High significant	Reject the null hypothesis
Task Significance		0.42	0.003	High significant	Reject the null hypothesis
Feedback		0.73	0.02	Significant	Reject the null hypothesis

Legend: p-value < .01 = High Significance, p-value < .05 = Significance, p-value > .05 = not significance

The result presented in Table 4 showed that task variety, task significance, and feedback are significantly related to work outcomes with a p-value result of 0.001 (task variety), 0.003 (task significance), and 0.02 (feedback) respectively. *Therefore*, we can reject the null hypotheses. This is similar to the study of Hussein (2020) with General TV Channels employees, the finding showed a strong association on job characteristics and job performance, albeit to varying degrees. Moreover, the study of Wambui (2018) found that skills variety, task identity and feedback affect the performance of employees.

However, for job autonomy, the result showed that it is not significantly related with the work outcomes of student interns with a result of 0.13 thus, the hypothesis is accepted. It contradicts the study of Muecke and Iseke (2019) on 319 research involving 151,134 participants, the result revealed that job autonomy often improved job performance, mostly by raising work motivation.

In terms of a positive relationship, the result showed a positive correlation coefficient between the core dimensions of job characteristics and work outcomes. For job autonomy and work outcome the correlation coefficient is 0.38, task variety is 0.60, task significance is 0.42, and feedback is 0.73, thus it indicates that all variables are moving in the same direction. The results of Prameswari's study (2019) showed that work engagement was significantly and positively correlated with each of the five categories of job characteristics. As per Jaadi (2019), although a correlation shows that two variables are correlated, it does not always mean that one effect the other (cause-and-effect relationship). However, the result of the study of Aan (2018) revealed that job characteristics has no significant relationship with employee performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study examines the relationship between job characteristics and work outcomes of intern students. Among the characteristics of the job, autonomy was found not to be a predictor of work outcomes of intern students. The researchers conclude that it is due to their inability to make their own decisions since they are just trainees within the companies. Therefore, consideration of job autonomy to improve work outcomes must be considered. Firms must design a job suited to virtual internships that will allow students to have autonomy toward assigned jobs. There are several meaningful findings from this study, specifically on task variety, task significance, and feedback. These were found to have a positive and highly significant relationship with students' work outcomes. This leads to the conclusion that providing multi-tasks to intern students can be a great motivation for them to be more productive and effective in the workplace. Further, a variety of assigned tasks was found to be a powerful tool to motivate the students to complete the tasks and see the result.

Among the job characteristics indicators, task significance and task variety are highly correlated with intern students' work outcomes. On this basis, presenting the importance of tasks, doing multi-tasks, and providing feedback on performance are essential. The findings suggest that organizations allow students to practice autonomy in the work environment to enhance intern work outcomes by designing a job that will allow them to have job autonomy. Additionally, the findings of this research can be used to further study the design of the organization's characteristics of the job that suits student trainees to provide a positive outlook and motivation based on their perspective.

The sample size of 150 students is insufficient to assess the validity of the data collected. A larger sample size might be more accurate in representing students' opinions. The respondents' demographics were not taken into account. Since demographic factors like gender, economic status, and ethnicity or race have a big impact on people's motivation, contentment, and performance, they must have been considered.

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